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Biomarkers of Stable and Decompensated Phases of Heart Failure with Preserved Ejection Fraction --Manuscript Draft--

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Manuscript Region of Origin:	Europe
Abstract:	<p>Background Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) is a disorder related to patient comorbidities and aging. Whether mitochondrial dysfunction is present during HFpEF decompensation versus the stable phase is largely unknown. The aim of the present study was to identify mitochondrial and cell metabolism blood biomarkers in older patients with acute and stable HFpEF.</p> <p>Methods Peripheral blood biomarkers were investigated in a group of eight to 12 patients aged 80–96 years and diagnosed with HFpEF first when they were in decompensated phase and then at least three months later in stable phase. Their data were compared to two control groups with an equal number of participants and sex proportions. One group was age matched and the other included individuals aged between 22 and 44 years.</p> <p>Results Decompensated patients experienced an increased mitochondrial superoxide production and mitochondrial mass, lower mitochondrial DNA copy number and LDHB expression, and higher lactate level compared to the stable stage. The stable phase was characterized by a sharp reduction in formate level. Multivariate analysis indicated that formate, lactate, and histidine can distinguish both of the HFpEF phases. Many of these parameters, including LDHB, lactate, formate, and mitochondrial mass, followed an age-related pattern, with acute HFpEF at its apex or nadir, suggesting that it represents an exacerbation of an aging-related process.</p> <p>Conclusions We identified distinct blood biomarkers of chronic and decompensated HFpEF phases. The data underlined the relationship between HFpEF and aging. These findings could be used to monitor patients and might be therapeutically targeted.</p>

Suggested Reviewers:	
Response to Reviewers:	<p>Manuscript Number: IJCJOURNAL-D-22-00377</p> <p>Replay to Editor and Reviewer comments:</p> <p>REVIEWER 1: The authors have addressed most of the prior comments and the manuscript reads better.</p> <p>Thank you</p> <p>Several comments:</p> <p>1. The line in the abstract " others like IL-t and HDL.....followed a similar tendency.... underling the relation....". It is not clear what this sentence means.</p> <p>We are sorry if we did not express this properly. We meant that for some markers (like IL-6) we observed a difference between young and elderly cases and HFpEF ones showed the extreme values without reaching significance, in the case of IL-6 between acute and stable phases. For simplicity and due to the word count limit, we deleted the sentence and now the text reads as follows: "Many of these parameters, including LDHB, lactate, formate, and mitochondrial mass, followed an age-related pattern, with acute HFpEF at its apex or nadir, suggesting that it represents an exacerbation of an aging-related process.</p> <p>Conclusions We identified distinct blood biomarkers of chronic and decompensated HFpEF phases. The data underlined the relationship between HFpEF and aging. These findings could be used to monitor patients and might be therapeutically targeted."</p> <p>2. The manuscript should be proof read by a copy writer and english/grammatical errors corrected</p> <p>We have proof read the manuscript with the assistance of International Science Editing</p> <p>3. The number of young and elderly controls should be stated clearly in the manuscript.</p> <p>We are also sorry that we did not explain this clearly enough. The groups of patients and controls were always the same number (in the 8 patients group we compared them with eight equal sex elderly and young control groups and then we added 4 females for the comparison when the patients were 12).</p> <p>We clarify this in the abstract: "Their data were compared to two control groups with an equal number of participants and sex proportions". And the "Subjects Characteristics" section: "All groups had the same number of individuals and sex ratio... Thus, all 12 patients and appropriate controls (four extra females for each control group) were ... the EC (n= 12) median age was ... and YCs (n= 12) were..."</p> <p>4. In the results section, the authors group their main findings into nice sub headings. The authors should do the same for the discussion section</p> <p>Thank you. We have divided the discussion section into subheadings.</p> <p>5. The limitations should be placed at the end of the discussion</p> <p>We placed the limitations at the end of the discussion.</p> <p>REVIEWER 2: Although authors partially responded to my concerns, I still have concerns below.</p> <p>Regarding my concern 2. Authors described "Sensitive, consistent and easy to obtain biomarkers are needed. However, classical blood biomarkers in HFpEF, including N-terminal pro b-type natriuretic peptide (NT pro-BNP), have been questioned and therefore new reliable ones have been searched." in the introduction section. However, it is clear that NT pro-BNP can be measured much easier than mitochondrial superoxide, mitochondrial</p>

mass, and mtDNA. Thus, authors should demonstrate the superiority of these new biomarkers over NT pro-BNP, listed in supplemental table 1, in the result section.

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We appreciate your suggestion to compare these markers with NT pro-BNP and we have done so. We have shown this in the new version of Figure 3 and the results. We also mentioned it in the discussion section.

In fact, our analysis indicates that formate, lactate, and histidine plasma levels are superior distinguishing both disease phases than NT pro-BNP in our patients: The accuracy of the model considering formate, lactate plus histidine was 87.5%, p-value (accuracy > no information rate) = 0.035, the out-of-bag (OOB) error of 25%, and the area under the curve (AUC) = 0.94.

“In contrast, the accuracy of the model for NT-pro-BNP was 50.0%, p (accuracy > no information rate) = 0.637, OOB error was 31%, and AUC was 0.69.”. We have incorporated this information to the results section 3.6.

Although this is encouraging, we have stated in the discussion: “Our data suggest that the use of these three metabolites might be superior to NT-pro-BNP in differentiating both disease phases in the context of very elderly patients’ HFpEF This will have to be validated in a larger cohort using techniques that might be feasible in the clinical context.”

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The literature has listed several potential causes for lactate accumulation in heart failure: insufficient supply of blood and oxygen to the peripheral tissues due to hypoxemia leading to hypoxia, low cardiac output, vasoconstriction, impaired tissue perfusion (as a consequence of congestion and elevation of central venous pressure), or inability of the tissues to increase oxygen extraction; higher oxygen demand due to adrenergic drive and neurohormonal activation; and impaired lactate clearance-inability to eliminate the produced lactate. In fact, Biegus J, et al did not find correlation between oxygen saturation and lactate in heart failure.¹

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Dear Editor,

We are submitting the reviewed version of the manuscript Ms. No. Submission IJCJOURNAL-D-22-00377, entitled “**Biomarkers of Stable and Decompensated Phases of Heart Failure with Preserved Ejection Fraction**” by Anguita E. and colleagues for your consideration. We include the response to the reviewers.

This work has not been previously published and has not been submitted for publication elsewhere while under consideration. All authors concur with the submission.

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author to whom correspondence and proofs are to be sent to communicate with the Editorial and Production offices:

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Sincerely,

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HIGHLIGHTS

- 1) Acute HFpEF patients have higher mitochondrial mass and normal for the age mtDNA.
- 2) These “congestive-like mitochondria” have elevated ROS production.
- 3) Increased mtDNA and low formate are marks of HFpEF stable phase.
- 4) Acute phase *LDHB* drop and lactate increase worsen the glycolytic pattern of aging.
- 5) Formate, lactate and histidine distinguish acute and stable HFpEF.

ABSTRACT

Background

Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) is a disorder related to patient comorbidities and aging. Whether mitochondrial dysfunction is present during HFpEF decompensation versus the stable phase is largely unknown. The aim of the present study was to identify mitochondrial and cell metabolism blood biomarkers in older patients with acute and stable HFpEF.

Methods

Peripheral blood biomarkers were investigated in a group of eight to 12 patients aged 80–96 years and diagnosed with HFpEF first when they were in decompensated phase and then at least three months later in stable phase. Their data were compared to two control groups with an equal number of participants and sex proportions. One group was age matched and the other included individuals aged between 22 and 44 years.

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Graphical abstract: Biomarkers of stable and acute stages of HFpEF

HFpEF Acute Phase

HFpEF Stable Phase

Biomarkers of Stable and Decompensated Phases of Heart Failure with Preserved Ejection Fraction

Short title: Biomarkers of stable and acute stages of HFpEF

Eduardo Anguita^{a,b,*}, Alberto Chaparro^{a,b}, Francisco Javier Candel^{a,c}, Carlos Ramos-Acosta^{a,b}, Neus Martínez-Micaelo^{d,e}, Núria Amigó^{d,e,f}, María José Torrejón^g, Guillermo Llopis-García^{a,h}, María del Mar Suárez-Cadenas^h, Mayra Matesanzⁱ, Juan González del Castillo^h, Francisco Javier Martín-Sánchez^{a,h}

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Hospital Clínico San Carlos Biobank

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

N.A. is stock owner of Biosfer Teslab and has a patent to commercialize the lipoprotein and glycoprotein profile described in the present manuscript. The other authors report no conflicts of interest.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

A.C., C.R.-A., and N.M.-M. performed experiments, acquired and analyzed data, and drafted the manuscript. N.M.-M., N.A., G.L.-G., M. M.S.-C. and M.M. selected patients, acquired and analyzed data, and drafted the work; N.M.-M., N.A., M.J.T., F.J.C., J.G.C., F.J.M.-S. and E.A. interpreted data and revised the manuscript critically. E. A. designed the work and wrote the final version of the paper. E.A. F.J.C. and F.J.M.-S. acquired the funding. All the authors approved the final version to be published.

TITLE

Biomarkers of Stable and Decompensated Phases of Heart Failure with Preserved Ejection Fraction

KEYWORDS

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ABBREVIATIONS

AHFpEF: acute heart failure with a preserved ejection fraction

EC: elderly controls

SHFpEF: stable heart failure with a preserved ejection fraction

YC: young controls

1. INTRODUCTION

Heart disease is a significant health problem linked to aging. Most elderly patients suffer from heart failure with a preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) [1,2]. The course of the disease is progressive, with several episodes of acute decompensation [3].

Changes in energy metabolism, comorbidities, and inflammation are considered to have a role in the origin and progression of heart failure (HF) [4]. However, it is difficult to distinguish abnormalities associated with aging from those linked to HF [1]. Thus, pathophysiology of HFpEF is not completely understood, nor is the change occurring during stable and decompensated periods. Previous studies have shown a mitochondrial dysfunction in HFpEF. However, most of this research has been performed in skeletal and cardiac muscle cells during the stable phase [5]. Invasive and highly specialized

1 endomyocardial biopsy has a very limited value for clinical use. Sensitive, consistent, and
2 easy to obtain biomarkers are thus needed. However, classical blood biomarkers in
3 HFpEF, including N-terminal pro b-type natriuretic peptide (NT-pro-BNP), have been
4 questioned and therefore new and more reliable ones are currently under investigation
5 [6]. Recently, circulating white blood cells have been claimed to represent a liquid biopsy
6 reflecting intra-cardiac metabolic condition. This may be particularly true for peripheral
7 blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs), as supported by several lines of evidence that include
8 the reactive oxygen species (ROS) level, mitochondrial morphology, and RNA and
9 protein expression [6]. A relevant example is the correlation between PBMCs and
10 lymphocyte mitochondrial ROS levels in chronic HF with disease severity and plasma
11 BNP and NT-pro-BNP [7,8]. Another method to search for these markers in blood is
12 metabolomics [9]. Considering that HFpEF is presently viewed as a systemic aged-related
13 condition [1], these holistic approaches may be particularly relevant. However, a
14 comparative analysis of functional changes in acute (AHFpEF) versus stable (SHFpEF)
15 phases in very old patients (ie 80 years of age and older) with HFpEF in the context of
16 aging is lacking. In particular, it would be clinically useful to detect these changes in
17 peripheral blood and to compare them to age-related ones. This would allow to better
18 understand and monitor this condition.

19 The present study aimed to describe biomarkers related to mitochondrial function and cell
20 metabolism using peripheral blood analysis between AHFpEF and SHFpEF among very
21 old patients in comparison with individuals of the same age and young controls.

22 **2. METHODS**

23 **2.1 Patients**

1 A total of 29 consecutive patients at least 80 years old who were admitted to the
2 Emergency department of a Tertiary University Hospital with decompensated HF were
3 enrolled in the study. They were diagnosed according to the European Society of
4 Cardiology (ESC) guidelines [10] and met all of the following criteria: clinical signs and
5 symptoms of HF, signs of pulmonary congestion on chest X-ray or pulmonary ultrasound,
6 and value of NT-proBNP of >1,300 pg/mL. Patients with left ventricular ejection fraction
7 of <50%, medical history of cancer, current infectious or inflammatory disease, and
8 steroid use or immunosuppressive treatment were excluded. Twelve patients with
9 AHFpEF and aged 80–96 years were included in the study and underwent the follow-up
10 procedure. The PBMCs were studied in eight of these patients (Supplementary Figure 1).
11 Elderly controls (ECs) were sex- and age-matched, independent, and had no oncological
12 or cardiovascular diseases. Young controls (YCs) were sex-matched, between 22 and 44
13 years of age, and without history of medication use or chronic disease.
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33 **2.2 Blood extraction**

34 The EDTA blood samples from patients with AHFpEF were taken in the first 12 hours of
35 presentation at the Emergency Department. The stable phase sample was acquired when
36 HFpEF was clinically stable and at least three months after the index event.
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46 **2.3 Mononuclear cell isolation**

47 PBMCs were obtained using Ficoll (lymphoflot; BIO-RAD, Hercules, CA, USA)
48 gradient centrifugation at 500 g for 30 minutes.
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56 **2.4 Nucleic acid extraction and conservation**

1 DNA was isolated by proteinase K digestion of PBMCs, followed by saline precipitation
2 [11]. RNA was extracted using a TRI reagent (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA)
3
4 according to the manufacturer specifications.
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9 **2.5 Flow cytometry**

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11 PBMCs were incubated at 37°C for 30 minutes in the presence of 200 nM MitoTracker
12
13 Green FM (Invitrogen-ThermoFisher, Waltham, MA, USA) for the mitochondrial mass
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15 or 5 µM MitoSOX Red (Invitrogen-ThermoFisher) for the superoxide radicals. Surface
16
17 markers CD14, CD3, and CD19 (BD Bioscience, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA) were added
18
19 for monocyte, T cell, and B lymphocyte recognition, respectively. The flow cytometry
20
21 data were acquired using a Gallios™ (Beckman Coulter, Brea, CA, USA) and analyzed
22
23 with Kaluza v2.1 (Beckman Coulter) software.
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31 **2.6 Mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) analysis**

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33 The mtDNA copy number was quantified using real-time polymerase chain reaction
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35 (PCR) through a comparison of mtDNA/nuclear DNA copy number coefficient, as
36
37 described previously [12]. Real-time quantitative PCR was carried out in an ABI 7500
38
39 Fast System with TaqMan Fast Universal PCR Master Mix (ThermoFisher-ABI,
40
41 Waltham, MA, USA) using the $2^{-\Delta CT}$ method.
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49 **2.7 Expression studies**

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51 RNA concentration was quantified using spectrophotometry with a NanoDrop equipment
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53 (ThermoFisher) and 1 µg was retrotranscribed with SuperScript IV Reverse Transcriptase
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55 using random hexamers following manufacturer recommendations (Invitrogen-
56
57 ThermoFisher). Real-time PCR was performed with 10 ng of cDNA for each assay.
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1 Expression assays (ThermoFisher-ABI) included *LDHA* (Hs01378790_g1) and *LDHB*
2 (Hs00929956_m1).
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4 Quantification used controls *TBP* (Hs99999910_m1) and *RPL30* (Hs00265497_m1)
5 (ThermoFisher-ABI), and was performed using the $2^{-\Delta CT}$ method.
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10 11 **2.8 ¹H-nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectrophotometry analysis of** 12 **lipoprotein, glycoprotein, low molecular weight metabolite, and lipid profiles** 13

14 Frozen plasma samples (250 μ L) were studied in Biosfer Teslab (Reus, Spain,
15 <https://biosferteslab.com/es/>) for the ¹H-NMR analysis. Lipoproteins and glycoproteins
16 were analyzed using the ¹H-NMR-based Liposcale[®] test, as previously described [13,14].
17
18 Low molecular weight metabolites were identified and quantified with the 1D Carr-
19 Purcell-Meiboom-Gill spectra using an adaptation of Dolphin software [15].
20
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22 Lipophilic extracts were obtained from 200 μ L aliquots of freshly thawed plasma using
23 the BUME method [16] with slight modifications. Quantification of the lipid signals in
24 the ¹H-NMR spectra was carried out with LipSpin [15], an in-house software based on
25 Matlab. Resonance assignments were carried out based on the literature values [17].
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41 **2.9 Biochemical parameters**

42 IL-6 was analyzed using electro-chemiluminescence (ECLIA) with Elecsys IL-6 kit in a
43 Cobas E-411 (Roche Diagnostics, Basel, Switzerland), according to manufacturer
44 recommendations. C-reactive protein (CRP) was studied in a Dimension Vista[®]
45 (Siemens Healthineers, Erlangen, Germany). When CRP was below 0.29 mg/dL, the
46 value was set to 0.2 mg/dL.
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58 **2.10 Ethics and statistical analysis**

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1 All patients provided written informed consent. The study was approved by the institution
2 ethics committee and followed the Declaration of Helsinki. The Wilcoxon test was
3 performed to analyze paired groups (the same patients in AHFpEF and SHFpEF). The
4 Mann-Whitney test was used for comparisons between patients and controls. Differences
5 between the groups were considered significant if $p < 0.05$. A three-step multivariate
6 analysis was performed with the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ data in HFpEF patients to identify important
7 metabolites related to the AHFpEF or SHFpEF. In the first step, candidate variables were
8 identified using the Wilcoxon rank-sum test and the random forest and partial least
9 squares discriminant analysis (PLS-DA). In the second step, variables were selected
10 based on their overlapping in a Venn diagram. In the third step, the relevance of the
11 variables was evaluated using a principal component analysis (PCA) and receiver
12 operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis. Statistical analyses were performed using
13 Prims 6 (Graphpad) and R Bioconductor 4.0.4.

34 **3. RESULTS**

39 **3.1 Subject characteristics**

40 First, eight patients (five males and three females) with PBMC and plasma samples were
41 studied. Their median age was 87 years (83–96 range). The mean time between samples
42 in acute and stable phases was 192 ± 50 days. ECs were 88.5 (80–100) years old (cases
43 vs. controls $p = 0.673$) and YCs were 28 (22–44) years old. All groups had the same
44 number of individuals and sex ratio. Four additional female patients only had plasma
45 samples. Thus, all 12 patients and appropriate controls (four extra females for each
46 control group) were analyzed for the plasma studies. The 12-patient AHFpEF group was
47 87 (80–96) years old. The mean time to the SHFpEF analysis was 207.5 ± 59.2 days, the
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1 EC (n = 12) median age was 88 (80–100) years (AHFpEF patients vs. ECs: p = 0.931)
2 and YCs (n = 12) were 29 (22–44) years old (Table 1, Supplementary Table 1, and
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5 Supplementary Table 2).
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10 **3.2 Superoxide production in mitochondria is increased in AHFpEF**

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12 Cardiomyocytes and PBMCs in chronic HF patients have elevated ROS levels and
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14 mitochondrial damage [5-8]. Therefore, we first wondered whether mitochondrial
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16 abnormalities were present in PBMCs and if they could be related to a particular phase
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18 of the disease or be a general age-associated finding.
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21 An increase in mitochondrial superoxide level was identified in peripheral blood
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23 monocytes and T and B lymphocytes in AHFpEF compared to SHFpEF (p = 0.039, p =
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25 0.0078, and p = 0.012, respectively; Figure 1A).
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29 Remarkably, mitochondrial superoxide level in SHFpEF was similar to that detected in
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31 YCs, with a significant reduction compared to ECs' T and B lymphocyte levels (SHFpEF
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33 vs. ECs: p = 0.021, p = 0.050 respectively; Figure 1A).
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39 **3.3 Mitochondrial mass and mtDNA show distinctive, opposite patterns in acute and** 40 41 **stable phases**

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43 Mitochondrial content and several related markers have also been investigated in HFpEF
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45 [5]. We observed that monocytes and T and B lymphocytes from patients with AHFpEF
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47 showed a significantly higher mitochondrial mass than those with SHFpEF (p = 0.039, p
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49 = 0.027, p = 0.019, respectively). Then, the mitochondrial mass became similar to the
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51 amount in ECs' monocytes and T lymphocytes. YCs showed the lowest mitochondrial
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53 mass (Figure 1B).
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1 The mtDNA copy number was similar in the acute phase and ECs, but increased later in
2 the stable period (AHFpEF vs. SHFpEF $p = 0.023$; Figure 2A). Therefore, mitochondrial
3 mass and mtDNA followed opposite patterns.
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10 **3.4 Metabolic studies suggest that acute patients require stress energy sources and** 11 **reveal formate as a unique marker of stable disease**

12 Previously described mitochondrial changes might be linked to modifications in cell
13 metabolism. First, we analyzed the expression of the key genes in glycolytic metabolism
14 lactate dehydrogenase A (*LDHA*) and B (*LDHB*). A reduction in *LDHB* but not in *LDHA*
15 (not shown) was identified during decompensation (AHFpEF vs. SHFpEF: $p = 0.0031$;
16 Figure 2B and Supplementary Figure 2). When the *LDHB* expression was compared in
17 patients and controls, an age-dependent impact was identified. In SHFpEF, patients
18 showed *LDHB* levels similar to those in the age-matched controls, but the young group
19 had a significantly higher *LDHB* level ($p = 0.0080$ and $p = 0.00028$ when comparing
20 AHFpEF with ECs and YCs, respectively; and $p = 0.020$, $p = 0.0090$, respectively, when
21 SHFpEF and ECs were compared to YCs; Figure 2B and Supplementary Figure 2).
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39 To further confirm and understand previous results, we performed a metabolomics study
40 based on $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (Table 1). In keeping with the *LDH* levels, higher lactate levels were
41 detected in the AHFpEF compared to the SHFpEF ($p = 0.016$). As described previously
42 [18], no correlation was present between lactate level and oxygen saturation in these
43 patients ($p = 0.698$; Supplementary Figure 3). Lactate level was also related to age, where
44 patients with the SHFpEF and ECs showed similar lactate plasma concentrations, which
45 were significantly lower than those in YCs (SHFpEF vs. YCs and ECs vs. YCs: $p = 0.038$
46 and $p = 0.0020$, respectively; Figure 2C). Besides, a significant reduction in formate level
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1 was observed in the stable phase compared to the decompensation phase (AHFpEF vs.
2 SHFpEF, $p = 0.0078$; Figure 2D).
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4 HF has been associated with increased diameters of HDL lipoproteins, mainly owing to
5 a lower small HDL particle number [19,20]. This finding was confirmed in the acute and
6
7 stable patients (Supplementary Figure 4).
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10 Although different groups showed very homogeneous results, the study was extended to
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12 all 12 individuals. Equivalent lipoprotein, glycoprotein, lactate, and formate patterns were
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14 observed (Supplementary Table 2 and Supplementary Figure 5).
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21 **3.5 Inflammation profile is elevated in both acute and stable phases**

22 There is a correlation between HDL particle size and inflammatory markers [19,20]. In
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24 fact, inflammation is thought to be at the origin of HF [4]. Therefore, we analyzed if the
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26 levels of IL-6 and CRP inflammatory markers are associated with acute or stable HFpEF
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28 phases. Higher levels of both markers were confirmed in HFpEF. This was significant
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30 only in patients with AHFpEF when the smaller groups were analyzed (AHFpEF and
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32 SHFpEF vs. ECs: $p = 0.0070$ and $p = 0.0648$, respectively, for IL-6; AHFpEF and
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34 SHFpEF vs. ECs: $p = 0.0216$ and $p = 0.8749$, respectively, for CRP). Nonetheless, IL-6
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36 levels reached significance in both phases when the extended groups were analyzed
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38 (AHFpEF and SHFpEF vs. ECs: $p = 0.0005$ and $p = 0.0036$, respectively, for IL6;
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40 AHFpEF and SHFpEF vs. ECs: $p = 0.0003$ and $p = 0.4739$, respectively, for CRP).
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42 However, no significant differences were detected between acute and chronic phases
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44 (AHFpEF vs. SHFpEF: $p = 0.64$ for IL-6 and $p = 0.296$ for CRP when $n = 8$; AHFpEF
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46 vs. SHFpEF: $p = 0.569$ for IL6 and $p = 0.176$ for CRP when $n = 12$; Supplementary Figure
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48 6; Supplementary Table 2).
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3.6 Identification of the most important metabolites according to acute or stable HFpEF

To identify whether AHFpEF and SHFpEF can be distinctly discriminated, a three-step multivariate data analysis was performed based on the metabolomic parameters obtained using ¹H-NMR (Figure 3A–D). This analysis uses several statistical approaches for the identification of candidate variables, selection of the most important ones, and construction and validation of the model. In the first step, three different statistical methods were applied to the ¹H-NMR data to identify variables in which plasma levels were significantly modulated depending on whether the sample corresponded to acute or stable periods. The identification of important variables was based on the selection of significant candidates resulting from the Wilcoxon rank-sum test ($p < 0.05$) and the five most important variables obtained in the classification using PLS-DA. To select the most important variables, all of the candidate variables obtained in the previous step were represented in a Venn diagram. Variables that overlapped within at least two of the three methods were selected. Three variables, including formate, lactate, and histidine, were identified. In the final third step, the relevance of the selected variable panel for the classification of HFpEF patients according to their phase was validated using PCA as a non-supervised statistical method and ROC curve analysis.

Despite the small sample size, the accuracy of the model for formate, lactate plus histidine was 87.5%, p (accuracy > no information rate) = 0.035, with out-of-bag (OOB) error of 25% and area under the curve (AUC) of 0.94. In contrast, the accuracy of the model for NT-pro-BNP was 50.0%, p (accuracy > no information rate) = 0.637, OOB error was 31%, and AUC was 0.69.

4. DISCUSSION

1 The present pilot prospective study assessed mitochondrial and metabolic biomarkers in
2 blood during acute and stable phases among older patients with HFpEF. Serial patient
3 samples were compared at each disease phase with both age-matched and young controls
4 to differentiate adaptations to aging from HF-specific changes. Our data show metabolic
5 stress modifications in the acute phase supported by higher mitochondrial mass, ROS
6 production, and glycolysis: reduced expression of *LDHB* and accumulation of lactate in
7 plasma. High mtDNA copy number and low formate level were markers of the stable
8 phase (Figure 3E).
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20 **4.1 Mitochondrial mass and mtDNA**

21 HF in general has been associated with mitochondrial dysfunction and a compensatory
22 increase in glycolysis [4]. We observed that mitochondrial mass was increased in PBMCs
23 during the AHFpEF phase compared to SHFpEF. Mitochondrial mass in the AHFpEF
24 may increase to respond to higher energy needs. Therefore, patients who experience a
25 failure to increase mitochondrial content in the acute phase may be unable to achieve the
26 energy requirements to successfully overcome this clinical situation. Mitochondrial mass
27 decreased to the level of the age-matched controls during the stable phase. YCs had the
28 lowest levels, suggesting that the acute phase worsens the age-related effect. In fact, it
29 has been postulated that ageing-associated mitochondrial dysfunction may be partly
30 compensated by rising energy production through the increase of mitochondrial mass
31 [21].
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49 The mtDNA copy number has been used as an indicator of mitochondrial content,
50 although the relationship between both parameters has been questioned [22]. In the
51 present study, the mtDNA content and mitochondrial mass followed opposite directions,
52 suggesting that there is a mitochondrial disequilibrium. These “congestive-like
53 mitochondria” with increased mass and normal mtDNA content for age seem to be
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1 distinctive of the acute phase. A similar finding has been observed in mitochondrial
2 myopathy mice. The increased mitochondrial mass in this setting was considered an intent
3 to compensate respiratory chain deficiency [23]. Remarkably, the increased mtDNA
4 content was also a unique mark of the stable phase. This may be a compensation
5 mechanism. On the contrary, elder controls showed a reduced mtDNA content compared
6 to the young controls, in agreement with previous observations on cellular senescence
7 [24] and in human PBMCs [25,26].
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19 **4.2 Superoxide production**

21 ROS level has been proposed as a mechanism involved in mitochondria abnormalities in
22 HFpEF [5]. Interestingly, the level of mitochondrial ROS in PBMCs correlates with
23 disease severity and plasma BNP/NT-pro-BNP level in chronic HF [7,8]. In keeping with
24 this, we observed a consistent increase in mitochondrial superoxide in the HFpEF acute
25 phase. This may be a result of the aberrant mitochondria found in this stage. In addition,
26 increased ROS production is one of the mechanisms that induces mitochondrial
27 permeability transition pore opening that causes mitochondrial swelling [27] and might
28 be the origin of the higher mitochondrial mass in this phase, although other phenomena,
29 like changes in the mitochondrial fusion-fission balance, might be involved [5,24,28].
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43 Increased mitochondrial mass and ROS level have been found in senescent cells
44 [24,28,29]. In agreement with this, higher mitochondrial mass and ROS level were
45 observed in elder individuals compared to the YCs in this study. In this sense, the elder
46 patients' AHFpEF data represent the zenith of an aging-linked event that reverts in the
47 chronic phase.
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57 **4.3 Metabolic studies**

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LDHB was downregulated in the acute HFpEF phase with respect to the stable one in our patients. *LDHB* catalyzes the conversion of lactate to pyruvate. Consistently, *LDHB* downregulation decreases oxidative phosphorylation and enhances glycolysis [30]. In keeping with this, the highest lactate levels were observed in acute patients, returning to the same amount as in ECs when the disease stabilized. The lowest levels were present in YCs. These data suggest a more glycolytic phenotype in the HFpEF acute phase, reflecting an exacerbation of an aging-related process that could be linked to mitochondrial dysfunction [4]. Accordingly, an *LDHB* reduction and lactate increase have been associated with aging and age-related diseases [31-33], and glycolysis is a hallmark of cell senescence [29].

Low formate concentration was a remarkable marker of stable phase when compared to the acute phase and EC levels. Similarly, low formate plasma levels have been found in mitral valve disease [34]. In this condition, lactate level was also reduced, while acetone was elevated. However, similar lactate concentrations were present in the chronic period and ECs and acetone was increased in both acute and stable periods, with higher levels in the former. Thus, formate levels appear to be a unique metabolic marker of SHFpEF. This can be associated with persistent heart damage, as suggested by the reduced formate accumulation observed in human cardiomyocytes treated with cardiotoxic doxorubicin *in vitro* [35]. Mitochondria are a major source of formate [36]. Therefore, mitochondrial dysfunction can partly explain this finding. In the acute phase, formate increase can be explained by the higher energy requirements and the failure of mitochondria to supply sufficient energy in this state, since formate increases the glycolysis rate [37].

4.4 Inflammation

1 Systemic inflammation has been considered to have a causal role in HF, mainly HFpEF,
2 and can be related to oxidative stress [4] and aging [2]. In particular, elevation in
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4 inflammatory marker IL-6 level has been associated with HFpEF development [38]. In a
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6 recent report on different patients with either acute or stable HFpEF, IL-6 and CRP were
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8 elevated in acute decompensated cases [39]. Significantly elevated IL-6 and CRP levels
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10 were observed in our patients compared to controls. We also found a tendency to reach
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12 higher levels in the acute period compared to the stable phase. These data may suggest
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14 that chronic inflammation has a central role in HFpEF independent of the disease phase.
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17 The increase in IL-6 with age was also confirmed [40,41].
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23 **4.5 Multivariate data analysis**

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25 In contrast with the inflammatory markers, metabolic data clearly separated the HFpEF
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27 phases. Furthermore, three-step multivariate analysis identified three metabolites,
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29 including formate, lactate, and histidine, whose plasma levels were a determinant for the
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31 classification between decompensated or stable HFpEF. Our data suggest that the use of
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33 these three metabolites might be superior to NT-pro-BNP in differentiating both disease
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35 phases in the context of very elderly patients' HFpEF. This will have to be validated in a
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37 larger cohort using techniques that might be feasible in the clinical context.
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42 Formate and lactate levels are likely increased in the AHFpEF as result of the enhanced
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44 glycolysis rate. In contrast, histidine levels are reduced in AHFpEF. Besides its role in
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46 protein synthesis, histidine stands out due to its protective antioxidant properties as a
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48 scavenger of toxic oxygen species in different contexts [42], including in the
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50 mitochondria [43]. Reduced histidine levels have been previously found in HF and were
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52 related to increased glycolysis [44]. Therefore, the results obtained in these analyses
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54 support our findings regarding the defects in mitochondrial functionality and energy
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56 metabolism in AHFpEF.
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4.6 Limitations

The main limitation of the present study is the small number of cases. This is conditioned by their very advanced age. In addition, the exclusion criteria allowed to include a more homogeneous group, but further limited the number. Moreover, the difficulty to follow-up very old patients, particularly new ones after the COVID-19 pandemic, had a crucial impact on the study. The group size was lower for the PBMC analysis ($n = 8$) because the need for collecting samples during the first hours of admission affected their processing. To reduce bias, these eight patients were analyzed independently and their metabolomic data were confirmed with four additional patients without PBMCs. Although numbers were reduced, the small variation within each patient and control groups and data consistency when the number of cases was increased support the validity of our results. The analysis of the statistical power and D Cohen effect size for the most important parameters supports this (for acute vs. stable phases, the range of these studies is 0.608–0.995 and 1.207–2.229, respectively, for T cell and monocyte mitochondrial mass and superoxide, mtDNA, *LDHB*, lactate, and formate data). Our results were also consistent with previous findings, including HDL lipoprotein size [19,20] and others that were discussed above. Nonetheless, all of the data will have to be validated in the future.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We found increased mitochondrial superoxide and data for enhanced glycolysis in the decompensated HFpEF phase in comparison to the stable phase in PBMCs. In addition, acute patients had congestive mitochondria with a higher mitochondrial mass. On the other hand, the stable phase was characterized by a high mtDNA content and low formate level (Figure 3E). Formate, lactate, and histidine distinguished both of the HFpEF phases.

1 When these markers were compared in these very old HFpEF patients with the elderly
2 and young controls, AHFpEF resembled an extreme aging process. These findings could
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4 be used to monitor patients and might indicate appropriate treatments.
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FIGURE LEGENDS

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5 **Figure 1. Mitochondrial superoxide and mass increases in AHFpEF peripheral**
6 **blood mononuclear cells.** A: analysis of superoxide production in mitochondria by
7 MitoSOX Red flow cytometry assessment in PBMCs stained with CD3, CD19 and CD14
8 surface markers for T-lymphocytes, B-lymphocytes and monocytes identification as
9 indicated, of acute and stable phases of HFpEF (AHF and SHF, respectively), elderly and
10 young controls (EC and YC, respectively). Plots show means \pm SEM. Wilcoxon test was
11 performed to analyze paired groups and Mann-Whitney test analysis for comparison
12 between patient and control groups. B: flow cytometry MitoTracker Green FM analysis,
13 showing mitochondrial mass. Analysis and plot as in A. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ and
14 *** $p < 0.001$.

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31 **Figure 2. Metabolic and mitochondrial studies in HFpEF peripheral blood**
32 **leukocytes suggest acute patients have a glycolytic phenotype and reveals low**
33 **formate and high mtDNA as markers of stable disease.** A: mtDNA copy number. B:
34 real time RT-PCR analysis of *LDHB* expression. C and D: lactate and formate levels (left
35 and right, respectively), measured by $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrophotometry analysis. Plots follow
36 Figure 1 and show means \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ and *** $p < 0.001$.

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48 **Figure 3. Biomarkers associated with AHFpEF or SHFpEF.** A: three-step data
49 analysis, (including the Wilcoxon's rank-sum test ($p < 0.05$), the top 5 most important
50 variables identified by a Random Forest analysis, and the 5 variables with highest variable
51 importance in projection (VIP) using a PLS-DA) used to identify the most important
52 metabolites of acute and stable phase. B: Venn diagram reporting the overlapping
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1 variable identification from the 3 statistical models. C and D: validation of the
2 classification capacity of the selected metabolic panel using a PCA and a ROC curve,
3
4 respectively; NT-pro-BNP ROC curve is also displayed. E: summary of the study main
5 findings, including mitochondrial central metabolic pathways, involved in the adaptation
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7 to AHFpEF compared to SHFpEF. Variables in bold were quantified in this study; the
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9 direction of arrows indicates increase or decrease of metabolite in acute versus stable
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11 HFpEF.
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Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Table 1. Epidemiological and biochemical data. Lipoprotein, glycoprotein, low molecular weight, and lipid profile determined by ¹H-NMR.

	AHF	SHF	EC	YC	Overall p- value	AHF vs SHF Paired p- value	p AHF vs EC	p AHF vs YC	p EC vs SHF	p EC vs YC	p SHF vs YC
	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>							
Characteristics of population											
Sex:					1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Female	3 (37.5%)	3 (37.5%)	3 (37.5%)	3 (37.5%)							
Male	5 (62.5%)	5 (62.5%)	5 (62.5%)	5 (62.5%)							
Age (y)	87.0 [85.8;88.5]	87.0 [85.8;88.5]	88.5 [86.0;91.5]	28.0 [22.8;31.2]	<0.001	1.000	0.673	0.002	0.673	0.002	0.002
Inflammation											
IL-6 (pg/mL)	15.15 [9.37;19.71]	4.82 [2.99;8.22]	4.82 [2.99;8.22]	1.78 [1.50;2.10]	0.0001	0.640	0,007	0,0002	0,0648	0,0011	0,0002
CRP (mg/dL)	1.30 [0.73;2.05]	0.3 [0.2;0.41]	0.3 [0.2;0.41]	0.20 [0.20;0.20]	0.003	0.296	0,0216	0,0014	0,8749	0,0256	0,0769
Hepatic											
ALT (IU/L)	22.4 [13.2;33.1]	17.9 [12.1;21.6]	17.9 [12.1;21.6]	12.6 [9.9;21.9]	0.593	0.148	0,2747	0,4331	> 0,9999	0,9319	0,6657
Lipoprotein profile											

	AHF	SHF	EC	YC	Overall p- value	AHF vs SHF Paired p- value	p AHF vs EC	p AHF vs YC	p EC vs SHF	p EC vs YC	p SHF vs YC
	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>							
VLDL-Cholesterol (mg/dL)	13.4 [8.65;16.1]	16.6 [8.04;18.6]	15.9 [7.39;19.5]	7.95 [5.43;12.4]	0.421	0.844	0.916	0.415	0.916	0.415	0.415
IDL-Cholesterol (mg/dL)	9.34 [7.29;11.2]	9.29 [7.70;10.9]	10.5 [7.28;12.6]	6.26 [3.90;7.21]	0.146	0.945	0.916	0.148	0.916	0.148	0.148
LDL-Cholesterol (mg/dL)	110 [97.2;117]	117 [94.3;123]	128 [116;151]	118 [115;131]	0.125	0.844	0.214	0.230	0.230	0.634	0.517
HDL-Cholesterol (mg/dL)	55.5 [46.9;59.6]	53.0 [49.5;57.1]	63.8 [61.0;69.5]	62.0 [55.2;64.1]	0.251	0.844	0.413	0.413	0.413	0.413	0.413
VLDL-Triglycerides (mg/dL)	48.7 [39.1;62.7]	57.9 [34.4;72.8]	68.1 [45.8;93.4]	33.5 [31.6;53.7]	0.353	1.000	0.634	0.424	0.601	0.424	0.587
IDL-Triglycerides (mg/dL)	10.2 [9.44;11.5]	10.1 [8.78;11.3]	11.4 [8.36;13.7]	7.87 [5.88;8.63]	0.102	0.742	0.809	0.117	0.793	0.117	0.117
LDL-Triglycerides (mg/dL)	15.0 [13.0;16.7]	14.1 [13.1;16.8]	15.7 [13.6;18.0]	13.6 [11.0;14.7]	0.617	0.844	0.834	0.793	0.793	0.793	0.793
HDL-Triglycerides (mg/dL)	15.4 [13.2;16.5]	14.8 [13.2;15.5]	13.6 [11.4;17.4]	8.29 [7.39;13.5]	0.104	0.641	0.809	0.138	0.809	0.148	0.138
VLDL-P (nM)	36.1 [28.6;44.5]	42.7 [26.8;53.4]	49.3 [29.3;64.2]	24.1 [22.1;38.7]	0.292	1.000	0.809	0.312	0.693	0.312	0.312
Large VLDL-P (nM)	1.06 [0.78;1.36]	1.16 [0.71;1.30]	1.21 [0.88;1.77]	0.71 [0.58;1.08]	0.479	0.945	0.834	0.646	0.646	0.646	0.646
Medium VLDL-P (nM)	4.24 [3.46;5.28]	4.96 [2.31;5.75]	5.81 [4.75;6.81]	3.75 [3.06;4.54]	0.432	0.844	0.496	0.719	0.496	0.496	0.719

	AHF	SHF	EC	YC	Overall p- value	AHF vs SHF Paired p- value	p AHF vs EC	p AHF vs YC	p EC vs SHF	p EC vs YC	p SHF vs YC
	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>							
Small VLDL-P (nM)	29.8 [24.5;38.9]	36.2 [23.8;45.1]	42.1 [23.5;53.1]	19.7 [18.1;33.4]	0.256	1.000	1.000	0.415	0.693	0.279	0.279
LDL-P (nM)	1063 [950;1131]	1117 [917;1215]	1223 [1141;1478]	1120 [1044;1262]	0.149	0.641	0.165	0.496	0.346	0.517	0.529
Large LDL-P (nM)	182 [159;193]	184 [156;203]	197 [177;222]	190 [184;194]	0.533	0.945	0.587	0.587	0.587	0.916	0.899
Medium LDL-P (nM)	276 [230;355]	290 [226;342]	336 [287;424]	333 [308;376]	0.304	0.945	0.424	0.440	0.424	0.719	0.440
Small LDL-P (nM)	591 [551;606]	607 [577;637]	729 [626;755]	606 [558;706]	0.083	0.547	0.038	0.555	0.223	0.496	0.916
HDL-P (μmol/L)	27.4 [25.2;29.8]	26.4 [25.4;28.4]	31.0 [29.2;33.6]	28.3 [28.1;29.9]	0.096	1.000	0.186	0.555	0.176	0.176	0.258
Large HDL-P (μM)	0.29 [0.26;0.32]	0.28 [0.26;0.30]	0.29 [0.26;0.32]	0.27 [0.25;0.28]	0.644	0.777	0.916	0.634	0.916	0.634	0.634
Medium HDL-P (μM)	11.4 [10.1;12.1]	11.1 [10.3;12.0]	10.3 [10.1;12.0]	10.3 [9.96;10.9]	0.770	0.945	0.916	0.916	0.916	0.916	0.916
Small HDL-P(μM)	16.1 [14.8;17.5]	15.0 [13.9;17.1]	20.9 [18.4;22.4]	17.8 [17.1;19.9]	0.017	0.742	0.088	0.089	0.088	0.088	0.088
VLDL-Diameter (nm)	42.3 [42.2;42.5]	42.2 [42.1;42.3]	42.3 [42.1;42.5]	42.3 [42.1;42.5]	0.548	0.207	1.000	0.845	0.689	1.000	0.689
LDL-Diameter (nm)	21.4 [21.2;21.5]	21.3 [21.1;21.4]	21.2 [21.1;21.4]	21.3 [21.1;21.4]	0.762	0.461	0.916	0.916	0.916	0.916	0.916

	AHF	SHF	EC	YC	Overall p-value	AHF vs SHF Paired p-value	p AHF vs EC	p AHF vs YC	p EC vs SHF	p EC vs YC	p SHF vs YC
	N=8	N=8	N=8	N=8							
HDL-Diameter (nm)	8.39 [8.36;8.40]	8.39 [8.36;8.40]	8.27 [8.23;8.29]	8.30 [8.25;8.34]	0.004	0.945	0.041	0.027	0.027	0.381	0.019
VLDL-TG/VLDL-C	4.04 [3.81;4.27]	3.97 [3.51;4.69]	3.99 [3.86;5.52]	4.47 [4.21;5.85]	0.108	1.000	0.719	0.070	0.719	0.344	0.223
IDL-TG/IDL-C	1.13 [1.04;1.21]	1.10 [1.06;1.14]	1.11 [1.05;1.20]	1.26 [1.16;1.49]	0.247	1.000	0.916	0.283	0.916	0.283	0.283
LDL-TG/LDL-C	0.14 [0.13;0.16]	0.13 [0.12;0.14]	0.12 [0.11;0.15]	0.10 [0.09;0.12]	0.092	0.742	0.283	0.176	0.600	0.372	0.165
HDL-TG/HDL-C	0.25 [0.23;0.32]	0.28 [0.26;0.32]	0.22 [0.17;0.26]	0.14 [0.12;0.21]	0.050	0.844	0.352	0.125	0.212	0.186	0.138
Total Cholesterol (mg/dl)	186 [173;207]	198 [171;209]	208 [205;242]	199 [187;216]	0.229	0.844	0.352	0.372	0.372	0.372	0.555
Total Triglycerides (mg/dL)	90.0 [79.8;103]	101 [70.5;115]	119 [77.1;139]	66.6 [55.9;85.7]	0.258	1.000	1.000	0.311	0.311	0.311	0.311
Glycoprotein profile											
Glyc-B (μmol/L)	387 [377;465]	386 [367;423]	387 [373;408]	354 [347;370]	0.282	0.641	0.903	0.346	0.916	0.346	0.415
Glyc-F (μmol/L)	219 [208;234]	227 [208;236]	230 [213;248]	219 [212;234]	0.961	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Glyc-A (μmol/L)	664 [632;829]	667 [645;725]	748 [645;791]	655 [588;731]	0.832	0.840	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

	AHF	SHF	EC	YC	Overall p- value	AHF vs SHF Paired p- value	p AHF vs EC	p AHF vs YC	p EC vs SHF	p EC vs YC	p SHF vs YC
	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>							
GlycBound.Glyc.Free	4.89 [4.56;5.17]	4.68 [4.54;5.30]	4.77 [4.31;4.99]	4.39 [4.24;4.96]	0.517	0.844	0.753	0.623	0.753	0.753	0.623
H/W Glyc-B	4.87 [4.73;5.84]	4.86 [4.61;5.31]	4.86 [4.69;5.13]	4.45 [4.40;4.67]	0.319	0.642	0.903	0.424	0.916	0.424	0.496
H/W Glyc-A	20.9 [19.9;25.9]	21.1 [19.0;22.3]	21.1 [20.3;22.7]	18.6 [17.6;19.2]	0.108	0.640	0.916	0.138	0.916	0.138	0.186
Low molecular weight metabolites profile											
3-Hydroxybutyrate (mM)	0.06 [0.06;0.08]	0.07 [0.07;0.10]	0.05 [0.05;0.05]	0.04 [0.04;0.05]	0.044	0.641	0.106	0.106	0.106	0.404	0.106
Acetone (mM)	0.03 [0.02;0.04]	0.02 [0.02;0.03]	0.01 [0.01;0.02]	0.01 [0.01;0.02]	0.016	0.313	0.055	0.055	0.088	0.753	0.055
Alanine (mM)	0.27 [0.26;0.36]	0.33 [0.25;0.45]	0.37 [0.34;0.40]	0.26 [0.21;0.35]	0.240	0.742	0.223	0.634	0.634	0.223	0.587
Creatine (mM)	0.05 [0.04;0.08]	0.06 [0.03;0.07]	0.04 [0.02;0.07]	0.07 [0.05;0.09]	0.728	0.945	0.875	0.875	0.875	0.875	0.875
Creatinine (mM)	0.08 [0.06;0.11]	0.07 [0.05;0.09]	0.05 [0.04;0.07]	0.04 [0.03;0.06]	0.011	0.641	0.148	0.027	0.207	0.173	0.047
Formate (mM)	0.14 [0.11;0.17]	0.02 [0.01;0.05]	0.11 [0.01;0.15]	0.00 [0.00;0.01]	0.002	0.008	0.297	0.010	0.344	0.075	0.025
Glucose (mM)	4.69 [3.88;6.07]	4.14 [3.95;4.99]	4.23 [4.07;4.85]	3.91 [3.66;4.02]	0.225	0.461	0.753	0.230	0.753	0.230	0.230

	AHF	SHF	EC	YC	Overall p-value	AHF vs SHF Paired p-value	p AHF vs EC	p AHF vs YC	p EC vs SHF	p EC vs YC	p SHF vs YC
	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>							
Glutamate (mM)	0.12 [0.09;0.16]	0.11 [0.09;0.15]	0.16 [0.09;0.21]	0.08 [0.07;0.09]	0.203	0.460	0.440	0.415	0.555	0.279	0.279
Glutamine (mM)	0.35 [0.32;0.42]	0.35 [0.25;0.51]	0.37 [0.26;0.41]	0.34 [0.31;0.38]	0.938	0.742	0.916	0.916	0.916	0.916	0.916
Glycine (mM)	0.17 [0.16;0.26]	0.17 [0.16;0.22]	0.22 [0.18;0.24]	0.19 [0.18;0.20]	0.935	0.740	0.916	0.916	0.916	0.916	0.916
Histidine (mM)	0.05 [0.05;0.05]	0.06 [0.05;0.07]	0.06 [0.05;0.07]	0.06 [0.06;0.09]	0.037	0.195	0.258	0.020	1.000	0.298	0.258
Lactate (mM)	0.97 [0.72;1.03]	0.55 [0.39;0.68]	0.58 [0.50;0.61]	0.34 [0.30;0.42]	0.001	0.016	0.031	0.010	0.916	0.010	0.043
Tyrosine (mM)	0.04 [0.04;0.05]	0.05 [0.04;0.05]	0.06 [0.05;0.08]	0.05 [0.04;0.06]	0.127	0.945	0.138	0.916	0.186	0.138	0.916
Valine (mM)	0.18 [0.16;0.19]	0.17 [0.16;0.19]	0.20 [0.18;0.24]	0.21 [0.19;0.23]	0.109	1.000	0.311	0.107	0.311	0.916	0.107
Isoleucine (mM)	0.04 [0.04;0.05]	0.04 [0.03;0.05]	0.05 [0.03;0.06]	0.03 [0.03;0.05]	0.486	0.641	0.600	0.587	0.587	0.587	0.600
Leucine (mM)	0.08 [0.07;0.09]	0.07 [0.06;0.08]	0.10 [0.07;0.13]	0.08 [0.07;0.08]	0.355	0.250	0.517	0.817	0.517	0.517	0.585
Lipid profile											
Esterified cholesterol (mM)	4.38 [3.78;4.87]	4.68 [3.98;4.80]	5.00 [4.86;5.94]	4.72 [4.65;5.05]	0.055	0.945	0.107	0.258	0.107	0.230	0.298

	AHF	SHF	EC	YC	Overall p- value	AHF vs SHF Paired p- value	p AHF vs EC	p AHF vs YC	p EC vs SHF	p EC vs YC	p SHF vs YC
	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>							
Free cholesterol (mM)	2.19 [2.03;2.44]	1.99 [1.89;2.50]	2.44 [2.11;2.63]	2.16 [2.00;2.39]	0.462	0.742	0.693	1.000	0.691	0.693	0.693
Triglycerides (mM)	1.30 [1.16;1.54]	1.46 [1.02;1.79]	1.72 [1.11;1.96]	0.82 [0.72;1.37]	0.347	1.000	0.834	0.415	0.834	0.415	0.415
Glycerophospholipids (mM)	2.67 [2.29;2.78]	2.49 [2.30;2.70]	2.75 [2.62;3.17]	2.75 [2.55;3.01]	0.332	0.742	0.415	0.440	0.415	0.753	0.415
Phosphatidylcholine (mM)	2.20 [1.99;2.29]	2.06 [1.90;2.35]	2.37 [2.24;2.76]	2.44 [2.32;2.64]	0.098	0.844	0.212	0.148	0.148	0.916	0.148
Sphingomyelin (mM)	0.57 [0.54;0.65]	0.54 [0.53;0.62]	0.63 [0.60;0.65]	0.56 [0.53;0.58]	0.265	0.383	0.587	0.634	0.424	0.352	0.753
Lysophosphatidylcholine (mM)	0.50 [0.42;0.53]	0.47 [0.43;0.56]	0.50 [0.47;0.56]	0.53 [0.46;0.58]	0.783	0.742	0.809	0.809	0.809	0.809	0.809
PUFA (mM)	1.73 [1.57;2.29]	2.07 [1.74;2.56]	2.05 [1.44;2.40]	1.82 [1.55;2.12]	0.775	0.195	0.834	0.834	0.834	0.834	0.834
PUFA (mM)	3.45 [3.05;4.00]	3.53 [3.14;3.81]	3.61 [3.08;4.01]	3.70 [3.22;4.11]	0.972	0.945	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
PUFA (mM)	2.39 [2.13;3.24]	2.57 [2.07;3.02]	2.10 [1.52;2.46]	2.28 [2.00;3.00]	0.650	0.945	0.802	0.916	0.802	0.802	0.916
PUFA (mM)	2.01 [1.95;2.39]	1.88 [1.61;2.70]	1.97 [1.88;2.59]	1.91 [1.70;2.25]	0.680	0.641	0.809	0.809	0.809	0.809	0.834

	AHF	SHF	EC	YC	Overall p-value	AHF vs SHF Paired p-value	p AHF vs EC	p AHF vs YC	p EC vs SHF	p EC vs YC	p SHF vs YC
	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>	<i>N=8</i>							
Linoleic (mM)	3.31 [3.19;3.99]	3.56 [3.00;4.04]	4.35 [3.84;4.86]	3.95 [3.61;4.48]	0.230	0.844	0.283	0.283	0.283	0.809	0.440
SFA (mM)	5.14 [4.76;5.39]	5.13 [4.93;5.44]	5.13 [4.76;6.00]	5.04 [4.65;5.56]	0.929	0.844	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
w6 & w7 fatty acids (mM)	4.15 [3.80;4.96]	4.28 [3.44;4.84]	5.34 [4.49;6.00]	5.53 [5.08;6.57]	0.061	0.945	0.311	0.107	0.186	0.555	0.107
w9 fatty acids (mM)	2.99 [2.67;4.01]	3.12 [2.56;3.35]	3.57 [2.44;4.11]	2.94 [2.65;3.50]	0.869	0.383	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
w3 fatty acids (mM)	0.27 [0.23;0.30]	0.23 [0.22;0.33]	0.23 [0.21;0.32]	0.24 [0.20;0.28]	0.582	1.000	0.689	0.689	0.916	0.916	0.916
DHA (mM)	0.08 [0.04;0.10]	0.06 [0.05;0.08]	0.07 [0.05;0.10]	0.07 [0.03;0.10]	0.897	0.313	0.903	0.903	0.903	0.903	1.000
AA + EPA (mM)	0.72 [0.61;0.91]	0.75 [0.60;0.87]	0.62 [0.49;0.77]	0.62 [0.57;0.68]	0.554	0.641	0.693	0.693	0.693	0.834	0.693

Quantitative values are expressed as median and interquartile range [Q1-Q3]. TG: Triglycerides; C: Cholesterol, PUFA; Polyunsaturated fatty acids (four different PUFA signals); w: Omega; DHA: Docosahexaenoic; ARA: Arachidonic fatty acid; EPA: Eicosapentaenoic fatty acid. AHF, acute heart failure; SHF, stable heart failure; EC, elderly controls; YC, young controls.

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Alberto Chaparro, Carlos Ramos-Acosta, and Neus Martínez-Micaelo performed experiments, acquired and analyzed data, and drafted the manuscript. Neus Martínez-Micaelo, Núria Amigó, Guillermo Llopis-García, María del Mar Suárez-Cadenas and Mayra Matesanz selected patients, acquired and analyzed data, and drafted the work; Neus Martínez-Micaelo, Núria Amigó, María José Torrejón, Francisco Javier Candel, Juan González del Castillo, Francisco Javier Martín-Sánchez and Eduardo Anguita interpreted data and revised the manuscript critically. Eduardo Anguita designed the work and wrote the final version of the paper. Eduardo Anguita, Francisco Javier Candel and Francisco Javier Martín-Sánchez acquired the funding. All the authors approved the final version to be published.

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION: A.C., C.R.-A., and N.M.-M. performed experiments, acquired and analyzed data, and drafted the manuscript. N.M.-M., N.A., G.L.-G., M. M.S.-C. and M.M. selected patients, acquired and analyzed data, and drafted the work; N.M.-M., N.A., M.J.T., F.J.C., J.G.C., F.J.M.-S. and E.A. interpreted data and revised the manuscript critically. E. A. designed the work and wrote the final version of the paper. E.A. F.J.C. and F.J.M.-S. acquired the funding. All the authors approved the final version to be published.

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